

BENCZE MIHÁLY
FLORENTIN SMARANDACHE
**About the characteristic
function of the set**

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About the characteristic function of the set ¹

In our paper we give a method, based on characteristic function of the set, of resolving some difficult problem of set theory found in high school study.

Definition: Let be $A \subset E \neq \emptyset$ (a universal set), then the $f_A : E \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$, where the function $f_A(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } x \in A; \\ 0, & \text{if } x \notin A, \end{cases}$

is named the characteristic function of the set A.

Theorem 1. Let $A, B \subset E$. In this case $f_A = f_B$ if and only if $A=B$.

Proof.

$$f_A(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } x \in A=B \\ 0, & \text{if } x \notin A=B \end{cases} = f_B(x)$$

Reciprocally: In case of any $x \in A$, $f_A(x) = 1$, but $f_A = f_B$ and for that $f_B(x) = 1$, namely $x \in B$ from where $A \subset B$. The same way we prove that $B \subset A$, namely $A = B$.

Theorem 2. $f_{\tilde{A}} = 1 - f_A$, where $\tilde{A} = C_{E}A$.

Proof.

$$f_{\tilde{A}}(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } x \in \tilde{A} \\ 0, & \text{if } x \notin \tilde{A} \end{cases} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } x \notin A \\ 0, & \text{if } x \in A \end{cases}$$

$$= \begin{cases} 1-0, & \text{if } x \notin A \\ 1-1, & \text{if } x \in A \end{cases} = 1 - \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } x \notin A \\ 1, & \text{if } x \in A \end{cases} = 1 - f_A(x).$$

Theorem 3. $f_{A \cap B} = f_A * f_B$

Proof.

$$f_{A \cap B}(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } x \in A \cap B \\ 0, & \text{if } x \notin A \cap B \end{cases} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } x \in A \text{ and } x \in B \\ 0, & \text{if } x \notin A \text{ or } x \notin B \end{cases}$$

$$= \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } x \in A, x \in B \\ 0, & \text{if } x \in A, x \notin B \\ 0, & \text{if } x \notin A, x \in B \\ 0, & \text{if } x \notin A, x \notin B \end{cases} = \left(\begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \in A \\ 0 & \text{if } x \notin A \end{cases} \right) \cdot \left(\begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \in B \\ 0 & \text{if } x \notin B \end{cases} \right)$$

$$= f_A(x) f_B(x)$$

The theorem can be generalized by induction:

Theorem 4. $f_{\bigcap_{k=1}^n A_k} = \prod_{k=1}^n f_{A_k}$

¹ Together with Mihály Bencze

Consequence. For any $n \in \mathbb{N}^*$ $f_M^n = f_M$

Proof. In the previous theorem we write $A_1 = A_2 = \dots = A_n = M$.

Theorem 5.

$$f_{A \cup B} = f_A + f_B - f_A f_B.$$

Proof.
$$\begin{aligned} f_{A \cup B} &= f_{\overline{A \cap B}} = f_{\overline{A \cap B}} = 1 - f_{A \cap B} = 1 - f_A f_B = \\ &= 1 - (1 - f_A)(1 - f_B) = f_A + f_B - f_A f_B. \end{aligned}$$

Can be generalized by induction:

Theorem 6.
$$f_{\bigcup_{k=1}^n A_k} = \sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^{k-1} \sum_{1 \leq i_1 < \dots < i_k \leq n} (-1)^{k-1} f_{A_{i_1}} f_{A_{i_2}} \dots f_{A_{i_k}}$$

Theorem 7. $f_{A \cap B} = f_A (1 - f_B)$

Proof. $f_{A \cap B} = f_{\overline{A \cap B}} = f_A f_{\overline{B}} = f_A (1 - f_B)$.

Can be generalized by induction :

Theorem 8.
$$f_{A_1 \cap A_2 \cap \dots \cap A_n} = \sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^{k-1} f_{A_{i_1}} f_{A_{i_2}} \dots f_{A_{i_k}}$$

Theorem 9. $f_{A \Delta B} = f_A + f_B - 2f_A f_B$

Proof.
$$\begin{aligned} f_{A \Delta B} &= f_{A \cup B - A \cap B} = f_{A \cup B} (1 - f_{A \cap B}) = \\ &= (f_A + f_B - f_A f_B) (1 - f_A f_B) = f_A + f_B - 2f_A f_B. \end{aligned}$$

Can be generalized by induction:

Theorem 10.
$$F_{\bigcup_{k=1}^n A_k}^{\Delta} = \sum_{k=1}^n (-2)^{k-1} \sum_{1 \leq i_1 < \dots < i_k \leq n} f_{A_{i_1}} f_{A_{i_2}} \dots f_{A_{i_k}}$$

Theorem 11. $f_{A \times B}(x, y) = f_A(x) f_B(y)$

Proof. If $(x, y) \in A \times B$, then $f_{A \times B}(x, y) = 1$ and $x \in A$, namely $f_A(x) = 1$ and $y \in B$, namely $f_B(y) = 1$, so $f_A(x) f_B(y) = 1$. If $(x, y) \notin A \times B$, then $f_{A \times B}(x, y) = 0$ and $x \notin A$, namely $f_A(x) = 0$ or $y \notin B$, namely $f_B(y) = 0$ so $f_A(x) f_B(y) = 0$.

Can be generalized by induction.

Theorem 12.

$$f_{\prod_{k=1}^n A_k}(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \prod_{k=1}^n f_{A_k}(x_k).$$

Theorem 13. (De Morgan)
$$\overline{\bigcup_{k=1}^n A_k} = \bigcap_{k=1}^n \overline{A_k}$$

Proof. $f_{\overline{\bigcup_{k=1}^n A_k}} = 1 - f_{\bigcup_{k=1}^n A_k} =$

$$1 - \sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^{k-1} \sum_{1 \leq i_1 < \dots < i_k \leq n} f_{A_{i_1}} f_{A_{i_2}} \dots f_{A_{i_k}} =$$

$$\prod_{k=1}^n (1 - f_{A_k}) = \prod_{k=1}^n f_{\overline{A_k}} = f_{\bigcap_{k=1}^n \overline{A_k}}.$$

We prove in the same way the following theorem:

Theorem 14. (De Morgan) $\overline{\bigcap_{k=1}^n A_k} = \bigcup_{k=1}^n \overline{A_k}$.

Theorem 15.

$$\left(\bigcup_{k=1}^n A_k \right) \cap M = \bigcup_{k=1}^n (A_k \cap M).$$

Proof. $f \left(\bigcup_{k=1}^n A_k \right) \cap M = f \bigcup_{k=1}^n A_k \cdot f_M =$

$$\sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^{k-1} \sum_{1 \leq i_1 < \dots < i_k \leq n} f_{A_{i_1}} f_{A_{i_2}} \dots f_{A_{i_k}} f_M =$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^{k-1} \sum_{1 \leq i_1 < \dots < i_k \leq n} f_{A_{i_1}} f_{A_{i_2}} \dots f_{A_{i_k}} f_M^k =$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^{k-1} \sum_{1 \leq i_1 < \dots < i_k \leq n} f_{A_{i_1} \cap M} f_{A_{i_2} \cap M} \dots f_{A_{i_k} \cap M} = f \bigcup_{k=1}^n (A_k \cap M).$$

In the same way we prove that:

Theorem 16. $\overline{\left(\bigcap_{k=1}^n A_k \right) \cup M} = \bigcap_{k=1}^n \left(\overline{A_k} \cup \overline{M} \right)$.

Theorem 17. $\overline{\left(\Delta_{k=1}^n A_k \right) \cap M} = \Delta_{k=1}^n \left(\overline{A_k} \cap \overline{M} \right)$.

Application.

$$\left(\Delta_{k=1}^n A_k \right) \cup M = \Delta_{k=1}^n \left(A_k \cup M \right) \quad \text{if and only if } M = \phi.$$

Theorem 18.

$$MX \left(\bigcup_{k=1}^n A_k \right) = \bigcup_{k=1}^n \left(MX A_k \right).$$

Proof. $f \text{MX} \left(\bigcup_{k=1}^n A_k \right) (x,y) = f_M(y) f \bigcup_{k=1}^n A_k(x) =$

$$\sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^{k-1} \sum_{1 \leq i_1 < \dots < i_k \leq n} f_{A_{i_1}}(x) f_{A_{i_2}}(x) \dots f_{A_{i_k}}(x) f_M(y) =$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^{k-1} \sum_{1 \leq i_1 < \dots < i_k \leq n} f_{A_{i_1}}(x) f_{A_{i_2}}(x) \dots f_{A_{i_k}}(x) f_M^k(y) =$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^{k-1} \sum_{1 \leq i_1 < \dots < i_k \leq n} f_{A_{i_1} \cap M}(x,y) \dots f_{A_{i_k} \cap M}(x,y) = f \bigcup_{k=1}^n (MX A_k)$$

In the same way we prove that:

Theorem 19.
$$MX \left(\bigcap_{k=1}^n A_k \right) = \bigcap_{k=1}^n (MXA_k).$$

Theorem 20.

$$MX(A_1 - A_2 - \dots - A_n) = (MXA_1) - (MXA_2) - \dots - (MXA_n).$$

Theorem 21. $(A_1 - A_2) \cup (A_2 - A_3) \cup \dots \cup (A_{n-1} - A_n) \cup (A_n - A_1) =$

$$\bigcup_{k=1}^n A_k - \bigcap_{k=1}^n A_k.$$

Proof 1. $f(A_1 - A_2) \cup \dots \cup (A_n - A_1) =$

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^{k-1} \sum_{1 \leq i_1 < \dots < i_k \leq n} f_{A_{i_1} A_{i_2} \dots A_{i_k}} - f_{A_{i_1} A_{i_2}} = \\ & \sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^{k-1} \sum_{1 \leq i_1 < \dots < i_k \leq n} (f_{A_{i_1}} - f_{A_{i_2}} - f_{A_{i_1} A_{i_2}}) \dots (f_{A_{i_k}} - f_{A_{i_1}} - f_{A_{i_2}} - \dots - f_{A_{i_1} A_{i_2}}) = \\ & \sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^{k-1} \sum_{1 \leq i_1 < \dots < i_k \leq n} f_{A_{i_1}} \dots f_{A_{i_k}} \left(1 - \prod_{p=1}^k f_{A_{i_p}} \right) = \end{aligned}$$

$$f \bigcup_{k=1}^n A_k \left(1 - f \bigcap_{k=1}^n A_k \right) = f \bigcup_{k=1}^n A_k - \bigcap_{k=1}^n A_k.$$

Proof 2. Let $x \in \bigcup_{i=1}^n (A_i - A_{i+1})$, (where $A_{n+1} = A_1$), then there exists

k such that $x \in (A_k - A_{k+1})$, namely

$$x \notin (A_k \cap A_{k+1}) \subset A_1 \cap A_2 \cap \dots \cap A_n, \text{ namely } x \notin A_1 \cap \dots \cap A_n$$

$$x \in \bigcup_{k=1}^n A_k - \bigcap_{k=1}^n A_k.$$

Now we prove the inverse statement:

Let $x \in \bigcup_{k=1}^n A_k - \bigcap_{k=1}^n A_k$, we show that there exists k such that

$x \in A_k$ and $x \notin A_{k+1}$. On the contrary it would result that for any $k \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, $x \in A_k$ and $x \in A_{k+1}$, namely $x \in \bigcup_{k=1}^n A_k$, it results

that there exists p such that $x \in A_p$, but from the previous reasoning it results that $x \in A_{p+1}$, and using this we consequently obtain that $x \in A_k$ for $k = \overline{p, n}$. But from $x \in A_n$ we get that $x \in A_1$ using consequently, it results that $x \in A_k$, $k = \overline{1, p}$, from where $x \in A_k$, $k = \overline{1, n}$, namely $x \in A_1 \cap \dots \cap A_n$, that is a contradiction. Thus there exists r such that $x \in A_r$

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and $x \notin A_{r-1}$, namely $x \in (A_r - A_{r-1})$ and so $x \in \bigcup_{k=1}^n (A_k - A_{k-1})$.

In the same way we prove the following theorem:

Theorem 22. $(A_1 \Delta A_2) \cup (A_2 \Delta A_3) \cup \dots \cup (A_{n-1} \Delta A_n) = \bigcup_{k=1}^n A_k - \bigcap_{k=1}^n A_k$.

Theorem 23. $(A_1 X A_2 X \dots X A_k) \cap (A_{k-1} X A_{k-2} X \dots X A_{2k}) \cap (A_n X A_{n-1} X \dots X A_{k-1}) = (A_1 \cap A_2 \cap \dots \cap A_n)^k$.

Proof. $f_{(A_1 X \dots X A_k) \cap \dots \cap (A_n X A_{n-1} X \dots X A_{k-1})}(x_1, \dots, x_n) =$
 $f_{A_1 X \dots X A_k}(x_1, \dots, x_n) \dots f_{A_n X \dots X A_{k-1}}(x_1, \dots, x_n) =$
 $(f_{A_1}(x_1) \dots f_{A_k}(x_k)) \dots (f_{A_n}(x_n) \dots f_{A_{k-1}}(x_{k-1})) =$
 $f^{A_1}(x_1) \dots f^{A_n}(x_n) = f^{A_1 \cap \dots \cap A_n}(x_1, \dots, x_n) =$
 $f_{(A_1 \cap \dots \cap A_n)^k}(x_1, \dots, x_n)$.

Theorem 24. $(P(E), \cup)$ is a commutative monoid.

Proof. For any $A, B \in P(E)$; $A \cup B \in P(E)$, namely the intern operation. Because $(A \cup B) \cup C = A \cup (B \cup C)$ is associative, $A \cup B = B \cup A$ commutative, and because $A \cup \phi = A$ then ϕ is the neutral element.

Theorem 25. $(P(E), \cap)$ is a commutative monoid.

Proof. For any $A, B \in P(E)$; $A \cap B \in P(E)$ namely intern operation. $(A \cap B) \cap C = A \cap (B \cap C)$ associative, $A \cap B = B \cap A$, commutative $A \cap E = A$, E is the neutral element.

Theorem 26. $(P(E), \Delta)$ is an abelian group.

Proof. For any $A, B \in P(E)$; $A \Delta B \in P(E)$, namely the intern operation. $A \Delta B = B \Delta A$ commutative. The proof of associativity is in the XII class manual as a problem. We prove it, using the characteristic function of the set.

$$f_{(A \Delta B) \Delta C} = 4f_A f_B f_C - 2f_A f_B + f_B f_C + f_C f_A + f_A + f_B + f_C = f_{A \Delta (B \Delta C)}$$

Because $A \Delta \phi = A$, ϕ is the neutral element and because $A \Delta A = \phi$; A is the symmetric element itself.

Theorem 27. $(P(E), \Delta, \cap)$ is a commutative Boole ring with divisor of zero.

Proof. Because of the previous theorem it satisfies the commutative ring axioms. Now we prove that it has a divisor of zero. If $A \neq \phi$ and $B \neq \phi$ are two disjoint sets, then $A \cap B = \phi$, thus it has divisor of zero. From Theorem 17 we get that it is distributive for $n = 2$. Because for any $A \in P(E)$; $A \cap A = A$ and $A \Delta A = \phi$ it also satisfies the Boole-type axioms.

Theorem 28. Let be $H = \{f | f: E \rightarrow \{0, 1\}\}$, then (H, \oplus) is an Abelian group, where $f_A \oplus f_B = f_A + f_B - 2f_A f_B$ and $(P(E), \Delta) \cong (H, \oplus)$.

Proof. Let $F : P(E) \rightarrow H$, where $F(A) = f_A$, then from the previous theorem we get that it is bijective and because

$$F(A\Delta B) = f_{A\Delta B} = F(A) \oplus F(B) \text{ it is compatible.}$$

$$\text{Theorem 29. } \text{card}(A_1 \Delta A_n) \leq \text{card}(A_1 \Delta A_2) + \text{card}(A_2 \Delta A_3) + \dots + \text{card}(A_{n-1} \Delta A_n)$$

Proof. By induction. If $n = 2$, then it is true, we show that for $n = 3$ it is also true. Because $(A_1 \cap A_2) \cup (A_2 \cap A_3) \subseteq A_2 \cup (A_1 \cap A_3)$;

$$\text{card}((A_1 \cap A_2) \cup (A_2 \cap A_3)) \leq \text{card}(A_2 \cup (A_1 \cap A_3)) \text{ but}$$

$$\text{card}(M \cup N) = \text{card}M + \text{card}N - \text{card}(M \cap N) \text{ and thus}$$

$$\text{card}A_2 + \text{card}(A_1 \cap A_3) - \text{card}(A_1 \cap A_2) - \text{card}(A_2 \cap A_3) \geq 0 \text{ can be}$$

written as $\text{card}A_1 + \text{card}A_3 - 2\text{card}(A_1 \cap A_3) \leq$

$$(\text{card}A_1 + \text{card}A_2 - 2\text{card}(A_1 \cap A_2)) + (\text{card}A_2 + \text{card}A_3 - 2\text{card}(A_2 \cap A_3)).$$

But because of $(M\Delta N) = \text{card}M + \text{card}N - 2\text{card}(M \cap N)$ then $\text{card}(A_1 \Delta A_3) \leq \text{card}(A_1 \Delta A_2) + \text{card}(A_2 \Delta A_3)$. The proof of this step of the induction relies on the above method.

Theorem 30. $(P^2(E), \text{card}(A\Delta B))$ is a metric space.

Proof. Let $d(A, B) = \text{card}(A\Delta B) : P(E) \times P(E) \rightarrow R$.

1. $d(A, B) = 0 \Leftrightarrow \text{card}(A\Delta B) = 0 \Leftrightarrow \text{card}((A - B) \cup (B - A)) = 0$ but because $(A - B) \cap (B - A) = \emptyset$ we get $(A - B) + \text{card}(B - A) = 0$ and because $(A - B) = 0$ and $\text{card}(B - A) = 0$, then $A - B = \emptyset$, $B - A = \emptyset$ and $A = B$.

2. $d(A, B) = d(B, A)$ results from $A\Delta B = B\Delta A$.

3. In consequence of the previous theorem

$$d(A, C) \leq d(A, B) + d(B, C).$$

As result of the above three properties it is a metric space.

PROBLEMS

Problem 1.

Let $A = B \cup C$ and $f : P(A) \rightarrow P(A) \times P(A)$, where

$f(x) = (X \cup B, X \cup C)$. Prove that f is injective if and only if $B \cap C = \emptyset$.

Solution 1. If f is injective. Then

$$f(\emptyset) = (\emptyset \cup B, \emptyset \cup C) = (B, C) = ((B \cap C) \cup B, (B \cap C) \cup C) - f(B \cap C) \text{ from}$$

where $B \cap C = \emptyset$. Now reciprocally: Let $B \cap C = \emptyset$, then $f(x) = f(Y)$, it result, that $X \cup B = Y \cup B$ and $X \cup C = Y \cup C$ or $X = X \cup \emptyset = X \cup (B \cap C) = (X \cup B) \cap (X \cup C) = (Y \cup B) \cap (Y \cup C) = Y \cup (B \cap C) = Y \cup \emptyset = Y$ namely it is injective.

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Solution 2. Let $B \cap C = \emptyset$ passing over the set function $f(x) = f(Y)$ if and only if $X \cup B = Y \cup B$ and $X \cup C = Y \cup C$, namely $f_{x \cup B} = f_{y \cup B}$ and

$$f_{x \cup C} = f_{y \cup C} \text{ or } f_X + f_B - f_X f_B = f_Y + f_B - f_Y f_B \text{ and}$$

$$f_X + f_C - f_X f_C = f_Y + f_C - f_Y f_C \text{ from where}$$

$(f_X - f_Y)(f_B - f_C) = 0$. Because $A = B \cup C$ and $B \cap C = \emptyset$ therefore

$$(f_B - f_C)(u) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } u \in B \\ -1, & \text{if } u \in C \end{cases} \neq 0$$

therefore $f_X - f_Y = 0$, namely $X = Y$ and thus it is injective.

Generalization. Let $M = \bigcup_{k=1}^n A_k$ and $f: P(A) \rightarrow P^n(A)$, where

$f(X) = (X \cup A_1, X \cup A_2, \dots, X \cup A_n)$. Prove that f is injective if and only if $A_1 \cap A_2 \cap \dots \cap A_n = \emptyset$.

Problem 2. Let $E \neq \emptyset$ and $A \in P(E)$ and

$f: P(E) \rightarrow P(E) \times P(E)$, where $f(X) = (X \cap A, X \cup A)$.

a. Prove that f is injective

b. Prove that $\{f(x), x \in P(E)\} = \{(M, N) \mid M \subset A \subset N \subset E\} = K$.

c. Let $g: P(E) \rightarrow K$, where $g(X) = f(X)$. Prove that g is bijective and compute its inverse.

Solution.

a. $f(X) = f(Y)$, namely $(X \cap A, X \cup A) = (Y \cap A, Y \cup A)$ and so

$X \cap A = Y \cap A, X \cup A = Y \cup A$, from where $X \Delta A = Y \Delta A$ or

$(X \Delta A) \Delta A = (Y \Delta A) \Delta A, X \Delta (A \Delta A) = Y \Delta (A \Delta A), X \Delta \emptyset = Y \Delta \emptyset$ and thus

$X = Y$, namely f is injective.

b. $\{f(X), X \in P(E)\} = f(P(E))$. We show that $f(P(E)) \subset K$. For any $(M, N) \in f(P(E)), \exists X \in P(E): f(X) = (M, N)$;

$(X \cap A, X \cup A) = (M, N)$. From here $X \cap A = M, X \cup A = N$, namely $M \subset A$ and $A \subset N$ thus $M \subset A \subset N$ and so $(M, N) \in K$. Now we show that $K \subset f(P(E))$, for any $(M, N) \in K, \exists X \in P(E)$ so that $f(X) = (M, N), f(X) = (M, N)$, namely $(X \cap A, X \cup A) = (M, N)$ from where $X \cap A = M$ and $X \cup A = N$, namely

$$X \Delta A = N - M, (X \Delta A) \Delta A = (N - M) \Delta A, X \Delta \emptyset = (N - M) \Delta A,$$

$$X = (N - M) \Delta A, X = (N \cap \bar{M}) \Delta A, X = ((N \cap \bar{M}) - A) \cup (A - (N \cap \bar{M})) =$$

$$((N \cap \bar{M}) \cap A) \cup (A \cap \bar{(N \cap \bar{M}))} = (N \cap (M \cap A)) \cup (A \cap (N \cap \bar{M})) =$$

$$(N \cap A) \cup ((A \cap N) \cup (A \cap \bar{M})) = (N \cap A) \cup (\emptyset \cup M) = (N - A) \cup M.$$

From here we get the unic solution:

$$X = (N - A) \cup M.$$

We test $f((N-A) \cup M) = ((N-A) \cup M) \cap A, ((N-A) \cup M) \cup A$ but
 $((N-A) \cup M) \cap A = (N \cap \bar{A}) \cup M \cap A = (N \cap \bar{A}) \cap A \cup (M \cap A) =$
 $(N \cap (\bar{A} \cap A)) \cup M = (N \cap \phi) \cup M = \phi \cup M = M$ and
 $((N-A) \cup M) \cup A = (N-A) \cup (M \cup A) = (N-A) \cup A =$
 $(N \cap \bar{A}) \cup A = (N \cup A) \cap (\bar{A} \cup A) = N \cap E = N, f((N-A) \cup M) = (M, N)$. Thus f
 $(P(E)) = K$.

c. From point a. we get g is injective, from point b. we get g is surjective, thus g is bijective. The inverse function is :

$$g^{-1}(M, N) = (N-A) \cup M.$$

Problem 3. Let $E \neq \phi, A, B \in P(E)$ and

$f: P(E) \rightarrow P(E) \times P(E)$, where $f(X) = (X \cap A, X \cap B)$.

a. Give the necessary and sufficient condition such that f is injective.

b. Give the necessary and sufficient condition such that f is surjective.

c. Supposing that f is bijective, compute its inverse.

Solution.

a. Suppose f is injective. Then: $f(A \cup B) =$

$$((A \cup B) \cap A, (A \cup B) \cap B) = (A, B) = (E \cap A, E \cap B) = f(E), \text{ from where}$$

$A \cup B = E$, Now we suppose that $A \cup B = E$, it results that

$$X = X \cap E = X \cap (A \cup B) = (X \cap A) \cup (X \cap B) = (Y \cap A) \cup (Y \cap B) = Y \cap (A \cup B) = Y$$

$\cap E = Y$, namely from $f(X) = f(Y)$ we get that

$$X = Y, \text{ namely } f \text{ is injective.}$$

b. Suppose f is surjective, for any $M, N \in P(A) \times P(B)$, there exists $X \in P(E)$, $f(X) = (M, N), (X \cap A, X \cap B) = (M, N), X \cap A = M, X \cap B = N$. In special cases $(M, N) = (A, \phi)$, there exists $X \in P(E)$, from $X \supset A, \phi = X \cap B \supset A \cap B, A \cap B = \phi$.

Now we suppose that $A \cap B = \phi$ and show that it is surjective. Let $(M, N) \in P(A) \times P(B)$ then $M \subset A, N \subset B$ and $M \cap B \subset A \cap B = \phi$ and $N \cap A \subset B \cap A = \phi$ namely $M \cap B = \phi, N \cap A = \phi$ and $f(M \cup N) = ((M \cup N) \cap A, (M \cup N) \cap B) = ((M \cap A) \cup (N \cap A), (M \cap B) \cup (N \cap B)) = (M \cup \phi, \phi \cup N) = (M, N)$, for any (M, N) there exists $X = M \cup N$ such that $f(X) = (M, N)$, namely f is surjective.

c. We show that $f^{-1}((M, N)) = M \cup N$.

Observation. In the previous two problems we can use the characteristic function of the set as in the first problem. This method we leave to the readers.

Application. Let $E \neq \phi, A_k \in P(E) (k = 1, \dots, n)$ and

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$f: P(E) \rightarrow P^n(E)$, where $f(X) = (X \cap A_1, X \cap A_2, \dots, X \cap A_n)$.

Prove that f is injective if and only if $\bigcup_{k=1}^n A_k = E$.

Application. Let $E \neq \phi, A_k \in P(E) (k=1, \dots, n)$ and

$f: P(E) \rightarrow P^n(E)$, where $f(X) = (X \cap A_1, X \cap A_2, \dots, X \cap A_n)$.

Prove that f is surjective if and only if $\bigcap_k A_k = \phi$.

Problem 4. We name the set M convex if for any $x, y \in M$

$tx + (1-t)y \in M$, for any $t \in [0, 1]$.

Prove that if $A_k (k=1, \dots, n)$ are convex sets, then $\bigcap_{k=1}^n A_k$ is also convex.

Problem 5. If $A_k (k=1, \dots, n)$ are convex sets, then $\bigcup_{k=1}^n A_k$ is also convex.

Problem 6. Give the necessary and sufficient condition such that if A, B are convex /concave sets then $A \cup B$ is also convex /concave. Generalization for n set.

Problem 7. Give the necessary and sufficient condition such that if A, B are convex /concave sets then $A \Delta B$ is also convex /concave. Generalization for n set.

Problem 8. Let $f, g: P(E) \rightarrow P(E)$, where $f(X) = A - X$ and $g(X) = A \Delta X, A \in P(E)$. Prove that f, g are bijective and compute their inverse functions.

Problem 9. Let

$A \circ B = \{(x, y) \in R \times R \mid \exists z \in R : (x, z) \in A \text{ and } (z, y) \in B\}$. In a particular case let $A = \{(x, \{x\}) \mid x \in R\}$ and $B = \{(\{y\}, y) \mid y \in R\}$.

Represent the $A \circ A, B \circ A, B \circ B$ cases.

Problem 10.

i. If $A \cup B \cup C = D, A \cup B \cup D = C, A \cup C \cup D = B,$

$B \cup C \cup D = A$, then $A = B = C = D$.

ii. Are there different A, B, C, D sets such that

$A \cup B \cup C = A \cup B \cup D = A \cup C \cup D = B \cup C \cup D = D$?

Problem 11. Prove that $A \Delta B = A \cup B$ if and only if $A \cap B = \phi$.

Problem 12. Prove the following identity.

$$\bigcap_{i,j=1, i < j}^n A_k \cup A_j = \bigcup_{i=1}^n \left(\bigcap_{j=1, j \neq i}^n A_j \right).$$

Problem 13. Prove the following identity.

$(A \cup B) - (B \cap C) = [A - (B \cap C)] \cup (B - C) = (A - B) \cup (A - C) \cup (B - C)$ and

$$A - [(A \cap C) - (A \cap B)] = (A - \bar{B}) \cup (A - C).$$

Problem 14. Prove that $A \cup (B \cap C) = (A \cup B) \cap C = (A \cup C) \cap B$ if and only if $A \subset B$ and $A \subset C$.

Problem 15. Prove the following identities:

$$(A - B) - C = (A - B) - (C - B),$$

$$(A \cup B) - (A \cup C) = B - (A \cap C),$$

$$(A \cap B) - (A \cap C) = (A \cap B) - C.$$

Problem 16. Solve the following system of equations:

$$\begin{cases} A \cup X \cup Y = (A \cup X) \cap (A \cup Y) \\ A \cap X \cap Y = (A \cap X) \cup (A \cap Y). \end{cases}$$

Problem 17. Solve the following system of equations:

$$\begin{cases} A \Delta X \Delta B = A \\ A \Delta Y \Delta B = B. \end{cases}$$

Problem 18. Let $X, Y, Z \subseteq A$.

Prove that: $Z = (X \cap \bar{Z}) \cup (Y \cap \bar{Z}) \cup (\bar{X} \cap Z \cap \bar{Y})$ if and only if $X = Y = \phi$.

Problem 19. Prove the following identity:

$$\bigcup_{k=1}^n [A_k \cup (B_k - C)] = \left(\bigcup_{k=1}^n A_k \right) \cup \left[\left(\bigcup_{k=1}^n A_k \right) - C \right].$$

Problem 20. Prove that: $A \cup B = (A - B) \cup (B - A) \cup (A \cap B)$.

Problem 21. Prove that:

$$(A \Delta B) \Delta C = (A \cap \bar{B} \cap \bar{C}) \cup (\bar{A} \cap B \cap \bar{C}) \cup (\bar{A} \cap \bar{B} \cap C) \cup (A \cap B \cap C).$$

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